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Research Article

**ANTI-DIABETIC ACTIVITY OF METHANOLIC EXTRACTS
OF LEAVES OF NIGELLA SATIVA ON ALLOXAN INDUCED
DIABETIES IN RATS****Errabati Suresh^{*}, P. Geetha vani¹, Dr. D venkata Ramana¹**

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Abstract:

Diabetes mellitus is a most common endocrine disorder, affecting more than 300 million people worldwide. For these therapies developed along the principles of allopathic are often limited in efficacy, Carry the risk of adverse effects, and are often too costly, especially for the developing world. In order to identify complementary or alternative approaches to existing medications, we studied the anti-diabetic potential of leaves of Nigella Sativa. The acute oral toxicity studies of the extracts revealed no toxic effects up to the levels of 2000mg/kg b.wt. The aqueous and alcoholic extracts of 20 and 30mg/kg body weight of Nigella Sativa was screened for the presence of hypoglycemic and antidiabetic activity. In this study diabetes was induced by a single IP dose Alloxan monohydrate in 72hrs fasted rats. The FBGL was carried on 7th, 14th and 21st day and OGTT was measured on 8th, 15th and 22nd day. Glibeclamide was taken as the standard and the results are quite comparable with it. The studies were indicated that the leaves of Nigella Sativa are effective in regeneration of insulin secreting β -cells and thus possess antidiabetic activity. The aqueous and alcoholic extracts showed significant effect in decreasing the Fasting blood Glucose level and oral glucose tolerance test of rats and it's also showed good hypoglycemic activity in normal glycemc rats. The preliminary phytochemical analysis of the extracts of Nigella Sativa revealed the presence of Alkaloids, Flavonoids, Steroids, Tannins, Anthraquinones, Terpenoids and Cardiac glycoside as the possible biologically active principles.

Keywords: Nigella Sativa, Alloxan monohydrate, Glibenclamide, FBGL and OGTT.

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INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes is one of the most common non-communicable diseases and a serious life-long condition appearing worldwide. The etiology of diabetes is a complex interaction of genetic and environmental factors. It is a heterogeneous group of metabolic disorders characterized physiologically by dysfunction of pancreatic beta cells and deficiency in insulin secretion or insulin activity and clinically by hyperglycemia or impaired glucose tolerance and other manifestable disorders. It is an endocrinological syndrome abnormally having high levels of sugar in the blood. This may be either due to insulin not being produced at all, is not made at sufficient levels, or is not as effective as it should be.

Diabetes is still a serious health problem all over the world since it is associated with increased morbidity and mortality rate. When compared with the general population, mortality and morbidity increase in diabetes is mainly due to the associated chronic complications both specific (microvascular) and nonspecific (macrovascular). Since the disease prevails in both genders and in all age groups, the general public has a concern about its control and treatment¹.

Classification of DM

Diabetes is classified by underlying cause. The most common forms of diabetes are categorized as

Type 1, or insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (IDDM) - an autoimmune disease in which the body's own immune system attacks the pancreatic beta cells, rendering it unable to produce insulin and

Type 2, or non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (NIDDM) - in which there is resistance to the effects of insulin or a defect in insulin secretion.

Type 2 diabetes commonly occurs in adults associated with obesity. There are many underlying factors that contribute to the high blood glucose levels in these individuals. An important factor is the resistance to insulin in the body essentially ignoring its insulin secretions. A second factor is the decreased production of insulin by the cells of the pancreas. Therefore, an individual with Type 2 diabetes may have a combination of deficient secretion and deficient action of insulin. In contrast to Type 2 diabetes, Type 1 diabetes most commonly occurs in children and is a result of the body's immune system attacking and destroying the beta cells. The trigger for this autoimmune attack is not clear, but the result is the end of insulin production².

Multiple risk factors for the development of Type 2 diabetes mellitus³:

- Family history (parents with diabetes).

- Obesity (i.e., $\geq 20\%$ over ideal body weight or body mass index $\geq 25\text{kg/m}^2$).
- Habitual physical inactivity.
- Impaired glucose tolerance.
- Hypertension ($\geq 140/90\text{mm Hg}$ in adults).
- High density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol $\leq 35\text{mg/dl}$ and/or triglyceride level $\geq 250\text{mg/dl}$.

History

The term "Diabetes" was first used around 250 B.C. It is a Greek word meaning "to syphon", reflecting how diabetes seemed to rapidly drain fluid from the affected individual. The Greek physician Aretaeus noted that affected individuals passed increasing amounts of urine as if there was "liquefaction of flesh and bones into urine". The complete term "diabetes mellitus" was coined in 1674 by Thomas Willis. Mellitus is Latin for honey, which is how Willis described the urine of diabetics⁵.

Historical accounts reveal that as early as 700-200 BC, diabetes mellitus was a well recognized disease in India and was even distinguished as two types, a genetically based disorder and other one resulting from dietary indiscretion. Ancient Hindu writings document how black ants and flies were attracted to the urine of diabetics. The Indian physician Sushruta in 400 B.C. described the sweet taste of urine from affected individuals, and for many centuries to come, the sweet taste of urine was a key to the diagnosis.

Physicians have observed the effects of diabetes for thousands of years. One of the effects of diabetes is the presence of glucose in the urine (glucosuria). For much of the time, little was known about this fatal disease that caused weight loss of body, extreme thirst, and frequent urination. It was in 1922 that the first patient was successfully treated with insulin. Till the mid-1800s, the treatments offered for diabetes varied tremendously. A breakthrough in the puzzle of diabetes came in 1889. German physicians Joseph von Mering and Oskar Minkowski surgically removed the pancreas from dogs. The dogs immediately developed diabetes. Now that a link was established between the pancreas and diabetes, research focused on isolating the pancreatic extract that could treat diabetes. Dr. Frederick Banting succeeded in his experiments of isolating a pancreatic extract. The diabetic dog was kept alive for eight days by regular injections until supplies of the extract, at that time called "isletin", was exhausted. Experiments on dogs showed that extracts from the pancreas caused a drop in blood sugar, caused glucose in the urine to disappear, and produced a marked improvement in clinical condition.

Epidemiology⁶

Present status projects that incidence of diabetes is on rise. Present number of diabetics worldwide is 150 million and according to new estimates from researchers at the World Health Organization (WHO), there will be an increase of about 300 million or more by the year 2030 (Warner, 2004). Only in year 2001, about 441,004 deaths were registered and 49,855 of them provoked by diabetes, representing 11.2% of the total population. In United States, diabetes is the sixth leading cause of death. The prevalence of diabetes mellitus is rapidly increasing worldwide and India is estimated to have 31 million diabetics from the total population of the world. Diabetes is predicted to become one of the most common diseases in the world within a couple of decades, affecting at least half a billion people.

The driving force behind the high prevalence of diabetes is the rise of obesity, sedentary lifestyle, consumption of energy rich diet, etc. The diabetes epidemic is accelerating in the developing world, with an increasing proportion of affected people in younger age groups.

The prevalence of Type 2 diabetes is now at epidemic proportions. Type 2 diabetes has a significant impact on the health, quality of life, and life expectancy of patients, as well as on the health care system. Type 2 diabetes accounts for about 90-95 % of population while Type 1 diabetes accounts for about 5 -10% of the total population. In the past, Type 2 was rarely seen in the young, but recent reports describe Type 2 diabetes being diagnosed even in children and adolescent⁷.

SIGNS AND SYMPTOMS¹¹:

In both the types of diabetes, signs and symptoms are more likely to be similar as the blood sugar is high, either due to less or no production of insulin, or insulin resistance. In any case, if there is inadequate glucose in the cells, it is identifiable through certain signs and symptoms. These are quickly relieved once the diabetes is treated and also reduce the chances of developing serious health problems.

Type 1 Diabetes:

In type 1 the pancreas stops producing insulin due to autoimmune response or possibly viral attack on pancreas. In absence of insulin body cells don't get the required glucose for producing ATP (Adenosine Triphosphate) units which results into primary symptom in the form of nausea and vomiting. In later stage, which leads to ketoacidosis, the body starts

breaking down the muscle tissue and fat for producing energy hence, causing fast weight loss. Dehydration is also usually observed due to electrolyte disturbance. In advance stages, coma and death is witnessed.

Type 2 Diabetes:

Increased fatigue: due to inefficiency of the cell to metabolize glucose, reserve fat of body is metabolized to gain energy. When fat is broken down in the body, it uses more energy as compared to glucose; hence body goes in negative calorie effect, which results in fatigue.

Polydipsia: As the concentration of glucose increases in the blood, brain receives signal for diluting it and, in its counteraction we feel thirsty.

Polyuria: Increase in urine production is due to excess glucose present in body. Body gets rid of the extra sugar in the blood by excreting it through urine. This leads to dehydration because along with the sugar, a large amount of water is excreted out of the body.

Polyphagia: The hormone insulin is also responsible for stimulating hunger. In order to cope up with high sugar levels in blood, body produces insulin which leads to increased hunger.

Weight fluctuation: Factors like loss of water (polyuria), glucosuria, metabolism of body fat and protein may lead to weight loss. Few cases may show weight gain due to increased appetite.

Blurry vision: Hyperosmolar, hyperglycaemia, nonketotic syndrome is the condition when body fluid is pulled out of tissues including lenses of the eye; this affects it's to focus, resulting blurry vision.

Irritability: It is a sign of high blood sugar of the inefficient glucose supply to the brain and other body organs, which make us, feel tired and uneasy.

Infections: The body gives few signals whenever there is fluctuation in blood sugar(due to suppression of immune system) by frequent skin infections like fungal or bacterial or UTI(urinary tract infection).

Poor wound healing: High blood sugar resists the flourishing of WBC, (white blood cell) which is responsible for body immune system. When these cells do not function accordingly, wound healing is not at good pace. Secondly, long standing diabetes

leads to thickening of blood vessels which affect proper circulation blood in different body parts.

Effects of diabetes mellitus¹²

Raised blood glucose level

After the intake of a carbohydrate meal the blood glucose level remains high because:

- Glucose uptake and use by body cells is defective
- Conversion of glucose to glycogen in the liver and muscles is diminished
- There is gluconeogenesis from protein in response to deficiency of intracellular glucose.

Glycosuria and polyuria

The concentration of glucose in the glomerular filtrate is the same as in the blood and, although diabetes raises the renal threshold for glucose, it is not all reabsorbed by the tubules. The remaining glucose in the filtrate raises the osmotic pressure, water reabsorption is reduced and the volume of urine produced is increased.

This causes electrolyte imbalance and excretion of urine of high specific gravity. Polyuria leads to hypovolaemia, extreme thirst and polydipsia.

Weight loss

In diabetes, cells fail to metabolise glucose in the normal manner, resulting in weight loss due to:

- Gluconeogenesis from amino acids and body protein, causing tissue wasting, tissue breakdown and further increase in blood glucose
- Catabolism of body fat, releasing some of its energy and excess production of ketoacids.

Ketoacidosis

This is due to the accumulation of the intermediate metabolite, acetyl coenzyme A, which cannot enter

the citric acid cycle without oxaloacetic acid. In diabetes the amount of available oxaloacetic acid is reduced because glucose metabolism is reduced. As a result excess acetyl coenzyme A is converted to ketones, which are acidic. When these accumulate in the blood, the pH drops, causing ketoacidosis. Ketones are excreted in the urine (ketonuria) and by the lungs. The consequences are:

- Hyperventilation and the excretion of excess bicarbonate
- Acidification of urine and high filtrate osmotic pressure which leads to excessive loss of water (polyuria), ammonia, sodium and potassium
- Coma due to a combination of low blood pH (acidosis), high plasma osmotic pressure and Electrolyte imbalance.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The designing of methodology involves a series of steps taken in a systematic way in order to achieve the set goal(s) under the prescribed guidelines and recommendations. It includes in it all the steps from field trip to the observation including selection and collection of the medicinal plant, selection of dose value, standardization of protocol, usage of instruments, preparation of reagents, selection of specific solvents for extraction, formation of protocols and final execution of the standardized protocol. All this requires good build of mind and a good and soft technical hand to handle the materials and procedure in a true scientific manner.

Drugs and Chemicals

Drugs and Chemicals used in this study were of analytical grade and of highest purity procured from standard commercial sources in India.

Table No: 1 Drugs and Chemicals

<i>S.No</i>	<i>Materials</i>	<i>Company Name</i>
1.	Alloxan	Quali Kems Fine Chem Pvt, Ltd, Vadodara.
2.	Methanol	Changshu Yangyuan Chemicals, China.
3.	Alcohol	Changshu Yangyuan Chemicals, China.
4.	Glibenclamide	Sanofi India Ltd, Ankleshwar.

Instruments

Following instruments were required for the study:

Table No: 2- List of Instruments used for study

Name of the instrument	Source
Centrifuge	Dolphin
Digital weighing balance	Horizon
Glucometer	Horizon
Heating mantle	ASGI®
Refrigerator	Videocon
Soxhlet extractor	ASGI®
Condenser	ASGI®
Burette stand	Dolphin
Round bottom flask	ASGI®, Amar
Mixer	Videocon
Oven	ASGI®
Water bath	ASGI®
Stirrer/glass rod	ASGI®
Watch glass	ASGI®
Whatmann filter paper	Manipore microproducts, Ghaizabad.
Butter paper	ASGI®
Spatula	ASGI®
Rubber pipes	ASGI®

PLANT MATERIALS AND PREPARATION OF DRUG SOLUTIONS

Preparation of plant extracts

Preparation of Aqueous Extract:

Dried leaves of *Nigella Sativa* were taken about 20gms into 250ml beaker containing 200ml of water. The contents were mixed well and then the mixture was boiled upto 80-90°C for 4-5hrs. Further the extract was filtered with whatmann filter paper. The filtrate was boiled until the concentrated residue is formed. The concentrated product was sealed in sample covers and stored under room temperature and used for further experiment to check the activities.

Preparation of Alcoholic Extract:

Dried leaves of *Nigella Sativa* were taken about 20gms into 250ml beaker containing 200ml of Alcohol. The contents were mixed well and then the mixture was boiled upto 50-60°C for 4-5hrs. Further the extract was filtered with whatmann filter paper. The filtrate was boiled until the concentrated residue is formed. The concentrated product was sealed in sample covers and stored under room temperature and used for further experiment to check the activities.

Preliminary phytochemical analysis of the extracts

The extracts so obtained were subjected to preliminary phytochemical screening. Phytochemical studies were performed to identify the presence of various phytoconstituents as follows:

Alkaloids

Extracts were dissolved individually in dilute Hydrochloric acid and filtered.

a. Mayer's Test: Filtrates were treated with Mayer's reagent (Potassium Mercuric Iodide). Formation of a yellow coloured precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids.

b. Wagner's Test: Filtrates were treated with Wagner's reagent (Iodine in Potassium Iodide). Formation of brown/reddish precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids.

c. Dragendroff's Test: Filtrates were treated with Dragendroff's reagent (solution of Potassium Bismuth Iodide). Formation of red precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids.

d. Hager's Test: Filtrates were treated with Hager's reagent (saturated picric acid solution). Presence of alkaloids confirmed by the formation of yellow coloured precipitate.

Triterpenoids

a. Salkowski's Test: The extracts were treated with chloroform and filtered separately. The filtrate was treated with few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid,

shaken and allowed to stand. If the lower layer turns red, sterols are present. If the lower layer turns golden yellow triterpenes are present.

Saponins

a. Froth Test: The extracts were diluted with distilled water to 20 ml and shaken in a graduated cylinder for 15 mins. The formation of 1 cm layer of foam indicates the presence of saponins.

b. Liberman Burchard Test: The extracts were treated with chloroform and filtered. The filtrates were treated with few drops of acetic anhydride boiled and cooled. Concentrated sulphuric acid was added through the sides of test tube. The formation of brown ring at the junction indicated the presence of steroidal saponins.

Flavonoids

a. Alkaline reagent Test: The extracts were treated with few drops of sodium hydroxide separately. Formation of intense yellow colour less on addition of few drops of dilute acid indicates the presence of flavonoids.

b. Lead acetate Test: The extracts were treated with few drops of lead acetate solution. Formation of

yellow precipitate indicates the presence of flavonoids.

Phenolic and Tannins

a. Ferric chloride Test: The extract was treated with few drops of neutral ferric chloride solution. The formation of bluish black colour indicates the presence of phenolics nucleus.

b. Gelatin Test: To the extract, 1% gelatin solution containing sodium chloride was added. The formation of white precipitate indicates the presence of tannins.

c. Vanillin hydrochloride Test: the extracts were treated with few drops of vanillin hydrochloride reagent. The conformation of pinkish red colour indicates the presence of tannins.

Phytochemical screening of *Nigella Sativa*.

The present investigation concluded that the isolated compounds from the plant *Nigella Sativa* shows the various Pharmacological effects was determined due to the presence of different phytochemical compounds. Further study is needed for the isolation of the constituents present in the plant and its individual pharmacological activity should need to consider and ultimately it should be implemented for the benefit to human beings.

Table 3. Phytochemical screening of *Nigella Sativa*.

S.No.	Phytoconstituents	Aqueous	Alcoholic
1.	Alkaloids	+	-
2.	Flavonoids	-	+
3.	Steroids	-	-
4.	Tannins	+	-
5.	Anthraquinones	+	+
6.	Terpenoids	-	-
7.	Cardiac glycoside	+	+

Acute toxicity testing

Acute toxicity studies revealed that the alcoholic extracts of *Nigella Sativa* were safe up to 2000 mg/kg of body weight and approximate LD 50 is more than 2000 mg/kg. No lethality or any toxic reactions was observed up to the end of the study period.

Table No: 4- Effect of extracts of *Nigella Sativa* on fasting blood glucose level (FBGL) in normal rats.

Treatment	Dose (mg/kg)	Blood glucose level(mg/dl)		
		7 th day	14 th day	21 st day
Normal control	-	84.93±3.27	79.28±4.60	74.33±3.11
Glibenclamide	10	79.99±6.10	78.66±2.32	75.89±3.40
AQNS1	20	86.22±3.52	84.24±5.23	80.15±3.75
AQNS2	30	80.36±7.46	78.97±4.64	75.28±1.31
ALNS1	20	70.1±5.86	68.19±3.72	64.78±1.97
ALNS2	30	81.6±5.87	79.20±4.79	76.11±3.62

Values are expressed as mean± S.E.M. n=6. Significant values were compared with p<0.005, normal control Vs all groups. Parent thesis indicates % reduction in BGL.

➤ **Oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) -**

Both the aqueous and alcoholic extracts of *Nigella Sativa* significantly ($P<0.005$) suppress the rise in FBGL after glucose load (2g/kg) in rats, at first half-an-hour and upto 2hr time as compare with other groups extract Glibenclamide on 8th, 15th and 22nd day. While aqueous and alcoholic extracts produced significant reduction in FBGL. Glibenclamide (10mg/kg) showed ($P<0.005$) significant suppression in FBGL rise at first half-an-hour, 1hr and normalized FBGL within 2hr. The detailed results are summarized in Table No:5.

Table No: 5- Effect of extracts of *Nigella Sativa* on 8th, 15th and 22nd day in normal rats.

Treatment	Dose (mg/kg)	Blood glucose level(mg/dl)		
		8 th day	15 th day	22 st day
Normal control	-	86.15±1.72	90.26±2.84	92.61±1.93
Glibenclamide	10	81.21±1.79	78.27±3.74	75.11±6.50
AQNS1	20	87.26±3.21	84.12±2.36	80.37±6.75
AQNS2	30	79.87±1.33	75.29±1.54	71.47±1.26
ALNS1	20	83.77±0.76	80.35±0.91	75.68±0.76
ALNS2	30	72.18±3.58	69.76±0.44	61.51±0.65

Values are expressed as mean ± S.E.M. n=6. Significant values were compared with $P<0.005$. Normal control Vs all groups. Paranthesis indicates % reduction in BGL.

➤ **Effect of *Nigella Sativa* extracts on antidiabetic activity in alloxan induced diabetic rats**

The animals treated with 100 and 200mg/kg of aqueous and alcoholic of different extracts shown significant decrease ($P<0.05$) in FBGL on 7th, 14th and 21st day of treatment when compare to other groups of animals. The aqueous extracts have reduced more (%) in FBGL when compared to alcoholic extracts except standard group. The detailed results are summarized in Table No: 6

Table No: 6- Effect of extracts of *Nigella Sativa* on fasting blood glucose level (FBGL) in Alloxan induced diabetic rats.

Treatment	Dose (mg/kg)	Blood glucose level(mg/dl)		
		7 th day	14 th day	21 st day
Normal control	-	81.28±4.69	80.98±7.87	83.74±4.35
Diabetic control	10	298.20±13.21	275.14±10.02	253.31±15.55
Glibenclamide	10	260.11±18.39	249.78±12.05	231.56±15.85
AQNS1	20	370.61±14.71	363.18±19.61	336.87±19.10
AQNS2	30	384.73±12.69	370.88±17.96	353.27±18.33
ALNS1	20	294.78±11.41	276.64±14.88	225.70±15.90
ALNS2	30	210.13±15.64	191.21±16.86	165.90±10.38

Values are expressed as mean ± S.E.M. n=6. Significant values were compared with $P<0.05$. Normal control Vs all groups. Paranthesis indicates % reduction in BGL.

➤ **Oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) on 8th, 15th and 22nd day-**

Both the aqueous and alcoholic extracts of *Nigella Sativa* are significantly ($P<0.05$) suppress the rise in FBGL after glucose load (2g/kg) in rats, at first half-an-hour and upto 2hr time period as compare with other groups extract Glibenclamide on 8th, 15th and 22nd day. While aqueous and alcoholic extracts produced significant reduction in FBGL. Glibenclamide (10mg/kg) showed ($P<0.05$) significant suppression in FBGL rise at first half-an-hour, 1hr and normalized FBGL within 2hr. The detailed results are summarized in Table No: 7.

Table No: 7- Effect of extracts of *Nigella Sativa* on 8th,15th and 22nd day in Diabetic rats

Treatment	Dose (mg/kg)	Blood glucose level(mg/dl)		
		8 th day	15 th day	22 st day
Normal control	-	87.75±1.63	84.59±2.87	90.99±1.58
Diabetic control	10	288.10±12.69	297.00±19.55	326.57±14.99
Glibenclamide	10	368.78±18.10	310.88±11.73	290.41±18.55
AQNS1	20	260.36±16.62	243.70±16.40	218.36±11.90
AQNS2	30	290.84±11.30	286.78±13.78	275.98±19.75
ALNS1	20	266.42±18.11	223.56±17.87	198.63±17.99
ALNS2	30	356.85±12.61	335.76±15.28	290.66±10.86

Values are expressed as mean ± S.E.M. n=6. Significant values were compared with P<0.05. Normal control Vs all groups. Paranthesis indicates % reduction in BGL.

DISCUSSION:

Despite the fact that diabetes has high prevalence, morbidity and mortality globally, it is regarded as non curable but controllable disease. Different synthetic drugs, plant remedies and dietary modification play an effective role in the reduction of the suffering that it causes. The potential role of medicinal plants as antidiabetic agents has been reviewed by several authors. In order to identify the plants with antidiabetic properties various plants have been tested *in-vivo* using animal models, for example rats, against the complications caused by inducers of diabetes, and it has been established that many plants possesses the potential to lower the fasting blood glucose levels and besides help in improving other diabetic complications. The sustained reduction in hyperglycemia automatically decreases the risk of other major complications of diabetes. Effective glucose control is the key for preventing or reversing the diabetic complications and improving the quality of life of the diabetics.

Many natural active compounds have been isolated from plants of different species. These active principles are complex Alkaloids, Flavonoids, Steroids, Tannins, Anthraquinones, Terpenoids, Cardiac glycoside and others. These compounds have been shown to produce potent hypoglycemic, anti-hyperglycemic and glucose suppressive activities. These effects might be achieved by facilitating insulin release from pancreatic β -cells, inhibiting glucose absorption in gut, stimulating glycogenesis in liver and/ or increasing glucose utilization by the body. These compounds may also exhibit Anti-Inflammatory, Antibacterial, Antifungal and Cardioprotective activities, and restore enzymatic functions, repair and regeneration of pancreatic islets and the alleviation of liver and renal damage.

Crude aqueous and alcoholic extracts of leaves of *Nigella Sativa* at a dose of 20 and 30mg/kg showed significant effect on the glucose tolerance of rats and it also showed reduction in the fasting blood glucose levels of the normoglycaemic rats, thus revealing the hypoglycaemic nature of the extracts. The effect was more pronounced for both extracts. These findings indicate that the extracts might be producing hypoglycaemic effect by a mechanism independent from the insulin secretion e.g. by the inhibition of endogenous glucose production or by the inhibition of intestinal glucose absorption.

Alloxan monohydrate is one of the chemical agents used to induce diabetes mellitus in animals. It induces diabetes by dose dependent destruction of β -cells of islets of langerhans. It is a generator of free radicals of oxygen which cause extensive DNA damage. It was observed that single intravenous dose of alloxan exhibited significant hyperglycemia. Excessive hepatic glycogenolysis and gluconeogenesis associated with decreased utilization of glucose by tissues is the fundamental mechanism underlying hyperglycemia in the diabetic state. As the hyperglycemia induced by alloxan falls under category of mild diabetes and may reverse after a few weeks, the hypoglycemic effect of the plant in hyperglycemic rats was studied during 22 days treatment. The difference observed between the initial and final fasting serum glucose levels of extract treated hyperglycemic rat's revealed antihyperglycemic effect of leaves of *Nigella Sativa* throughout the period of study. The effect of the extracts was compared to that of reference standard, Glibenclamide and was found to be significant.

Phytochemical analysis of extracts of leaves of *Nigella Sativa* revealed the presence of secondary metabolites that have been shown to possess antidiabetic effect in other plants. Flavonoids,

alkaloids and Steroids which were responsible for the antidiabetic effect in other plants were also detected in the extracts of this plant. The presence of phenols in the plant could also be responsible for the antidiabetic effect have been shown to prevent the destruction of β -cells by inhibiting the peroxidation chain reaction and thus they may provide protection against the development of diabetes. Extracts of leaves of *Nigella Sativa* appear to be attractive materials for further studies leading to possible drug development for diabetes. Development of phytomedicines is relatively inexpensive and less time consuming; it is more suited to our economic conditions than allopathic drug development which is more expensive and spread over several years.

CONCLUSION:

The study was performed to find out the beneficial effects of two different extracts of leaves of *Nigella Sativa* in normoglycaemic rats and alloxan induced diabetic rats and the results reveal that the plant has beneficial effects on blood glucose levels.

In current scenario, herbs are the potent sources of medicines used in the treatment of various disease and disorders. Since, plants are used as medicine there is prompt need of evaluation of plant species, therefore, the present work was conceived to evaluate the phytochemical and pharmacological screening of leaves of *Nigella Sativa*. The Phytochemical evaluation has revealed the presence of Alkaloids, Flavonoids, Steroids, Tannins, Anthraquinones, Terpenoids, Cardiac glycoside.

The aqueous and alcoholic extracts had hypoglycemic activity because the presence of flavonoids which are rich in treatment of hypoglycaemia with less side effects. Flavonoids might be producing hypoglycaemic effect by a mechanism independent from insulin secretion e.g. by the inhibition of endogenous glucose production or by the inhibition of intestinal glucose absorption. The present study *Nigella Sativa* of both aqueous and alcoholic extracts was showed significant effect on glucose tolerance and also showed reduction in fasting blood glucose levels in normal diabetic rats.

The data of the blood glucose level of rats treated with Alloxan (150mg/kg body weight) produced diabetes within 72 hours. After 72 hours of Alloxan administered the blood glucose levels of rats were observed. It was observed that significant lowering of sugar in aqueous and alcoholic extract. The administration of different extracts at a dose of 20 and 30 mg/kg showed significant anti-hyperglycaemic effect at 22nd day which was evident

from the 7th day on wards as compared to standard. The aqueous and alcoholic extract of *Nigella Sativa* has showed better anti-hyperglycaemic effect of the extract on the fasting blood sugar levels on diabetic rats are shown in table. The decreasing blood glucose levels are comparable with that of 10 mg/kg of Glibenclamide. The Glibenclamide (10 mg/kg body weight) shows significant effect on compare to the initial and more significant effect on the 22nd Day compare to the initial. The aqueous and alcoholic extracts of 20 and 30mg/kg body weight shows significant ($P^* < 0.05$), effect.

Results of anti-diabetic activity in normal and alloxan induced rats the extracts established the scientific basis for the utility of these plants in the treatment of diabetes. The extracts have shown significant reduction in blood glucose levels in normal and alloxan induced diabetic rats and produced maximum anti-diabetic activity and are higher than the hypoglycaemic activity of Glibenclamide in the diabetic rats. In glucose loaded animals, the drug has reduced the blood glucose to the normal levels. It is possible that the drug may be acting by potentiating the pancreatic secretion or increasing the glucose uptake. In conclusion, these extract showed significant anti-diabetic effect in normal and diabetic rats after administration. Thus the claim made by the traditional Indian systems of medicine regarding the use of these plants in the treatment of diabetes stands confirms.

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